

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH:
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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti rektori, i.f.n., dotsent**

MUNDARIJA

1-SHO'BA. ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYASI ASOSIDA IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Барқарор ўсишни таъминлашда давлат компанияларини хусусийлаштириш масалалари.....	14
Ахмедов Хожиакбархон Дилшатович	
Бионар ва иншоотлар давлат кадастрини гат технологиялари асосида такомиллаштириш бўйича дастурлар ва ахборот тизимларидан фойдаланиш	18
Султанов Мансур Қиличович, Нарбаев Шарафатдин Кенгешович, Хасанов Исломхон Илхом ўғли	
Оборонно-промышленный комплекс Российской Федерации: основные тенденции развития системы управления предприятиями в условиях цифровизации.....	23
Кузнецов Виктор Павлович, Виноградов Никита Вадимович	
Application of green technologies to industrial enterprises: current situation analysis and future perspectives.....	26
Juraev Abbosbek	
Ердан самарали фойдаланиш ҳудудларни ривожлантиришнинг устувор омили.....	30
Чертовичкий Александр Степанович, Нарбаев Шарафатдин Кенгешович	
Финансовая структура предприятия как базис для эффективного управления финансами предприятия.....	37
Семенова Елена Вячеславовна, Цымбалов Сергей Дмитриевич	
Технологии блокчейн в управлении цепочками поставок: повышение прозрачности и устойчивости	39
Брехова В.О., Цыбуцинина И.Е.	
Kimyo sanoati korxonalari faoliyatini rivojlantirishda marketing kommunikatsiyasi strategiyalari.....	41
Sabirov Oybek Shavkatbekovich, Muminova Dildora Dilshadovna	
Hududlarda sanoat korxonalarini joylashtirish nazariyalari va strategik yo'nalishlari.....	46
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich	
Innovation iqtisodiyot sharoitida marketing konsepsiyalarining mohiyati.....	50
Asamxodjayeva Shoira Shukurullayevna	
Brendning yetakchi marketing vositasi sifatida kompaniyalar uchun mohiyati va ahamiyati.....	53
Achilova Nargiza Baxtiyorovna	
Korxonada bozor faoliyatini rivojlantirishda raqamli marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish	56
Karimjanova Ra'noxon Maxmudovna, Nosirov Husniddin Xusanboy o'g'li	
Implementation of the cobba doughlas model in the development of the экономай.....	58
Rustamova Mekhrigiyo	
Agrosanoat korxonalari faoliyatida raqamli savdo platformalari.....	63
Fayzullayev Shuhrat Sherali o'g'li	
Mahsulot diversifikatsiyasi asosida eksport potensialini oshirish yo'llari	67
Jo'rabayeva Sh.K.	
Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida aglomeratsiyalarning o'rni va roli	70
Mardonov Shohruh	
Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda marketingning roli.....	74
Anarbayev S.O., Xusenov Sh., Boltayev A., Muxtorov M., Yondoshaliyev A., Abdumalikov N., Tursunaliyev U., Qurbonov B., Toshpo'latov B., Ro'ziboyev D.	
The impact of Uzbekistan's WTO membership on economic development.....	77
Sadriddinov Ulugbek Jaloliddin ugli	

Концепции маркетинга для бизнеса и степень их цифровизации в современном обществе	80
Атакузиева Шахноза Рахматиллаевна	
Приоритетные направления дальнейшего развития бизнеса в Узбекистане	83
Каюмов Равшан Исмаилович	
Milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari va usullari	87
Xusniddinova Madina Javlon qizi	
State investment policy	89
Mohinur Rakhimova Dilshod kizi, Rakhimbayeva Diyora	
Интеграциялашган корхоналарда кластерли ёндашувларнинг хориж тажрибалари.....	91
Турсунова Зарнигор Рустамовна	
Инновацион ривожланиш шароитида малакали кадрларни тайёрлаш зарурати.....	94
Юсупов Қудрат	

2-SHO'BA. INNOVATION MENEJMENT KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Барқарор ривожланиш ва ҳудудларнинг “яшил” ўсиши: иқтисодий-экологик жиҳатларининг эконометрик таҳлили.....	98
Ражабов Н., Адилова М., Қаландарова Г., Хасанова Н.	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlari bilan vositachi eksport tashkilotlarining o'zaro hamkorligi samaradorligini baholash uslubiyoti	108
Nosirova N.J.	
“Яшил” иқтисодиётни амалга ошириш даражасини баҳолаш хусусиятлари	119
Хотамов И.С.	
Наманган вилоятида кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбирколикни ривожланиши.....	122
Каримжанова Р, Носиров Х.Х.	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish yo'llari.....	126
Луқманов Б.М.	
Правовые и организационные аспекты интеграции свободы слова и бизнес-инноваций в цифровую экономику узбекистана.....	128
Халилова Нигорахон Акмалджон кизи	
Innovatsion menejment konsepsiyalari asosida biznesni rivojlantirish	130
Utbasarov D.B.	
Assessing factors affecting the green economy	133
Rakhimova M.D.	
Xududlarda kichik va yirik korxonalarini innovatsion faoliyatini moliyalashtirish.	135
Bozorov I., Nematov N.	
Innovatsiyalar - tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishning muhim omili.....	139
Asamxodjayeva Sh.Sh.	
Роль приватизации государственного имущества в развитии негосударственного сектора экономики в узбекистане	142
Кадыров Т.А.	
Waste management activities and methods.....	145
Azlarova M.	
Статистический анализ взаимосвязи между количеством постоянных и сезонных работников в сельском хозяйстве.	147
Рустамова М.М.	

3-SHO'BA. MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR, YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR

Moliya va soliq sohasidagi muammolar, yechimlar va xorijiy tajribalar	153
Rafikova M. Sherboobyev D.O'.	
Меҳнат тақсимоти ва ихтисослашув жараёнларига бўлган турли хил ёндошувлар таҳлили	156
Шарипов К.Б.	
Bank tizimini raqamlashtirish - moliyaviy xizmatlarni rivojlantirish istiqboli va ustuvor yo'nalishi.....	158
Serjanov A.M.	
O'zbekistonda bank xizmatlarining rivojlanish holatiga bir nazar	161
Serjanov A.M.	
O'zbekiston respublikasida mikromoliya tashkilotlarining iqtisodiy faoliyati va kichik biznesni rivojlantirishidagi ahamiyati.....	164
Madaminova N.I.	
Fiscal and monetary policy of the state.....	167
Rakhimova M.D., Kasimdjanova B.	
The determinants of financial development in case of central asian countries	170
Otabaev Y.M.	
Initial research: are the current researched early warning indicators significant in identifying banking crises?.....	176
Berdiyev B. Sh., Masharipov S.M., Berdiyev J.Sh.	
Тижорат банклари фаолият самарадорлигини ошириш стратегиясини шакллантириш масалалари.....	182
Темиров А.А.	
Are the current researched early warning indicators significant in identifying banking crises?.....	188
Berdiyev B.Sh., Masharipov S.M., Berdiyev J.Sh.	
Anarxik jamiyatda iqtisodiy muammolar va ularga bo'lgan qarashlar	198
Qurbonov B.A., Muxtorov M.Sh., Yondoshaliyev A., Tursunaliyev U., Abdumalikov N., Boltayev A., Xusenov Sh., Toshpo'latov B., Ro'ziboyev D., Anarbayerov S.	
Bojxona to'lovlaridan imtiyoz va preferensiyalar qo'llashni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	200
Pardaev T. N., Tursinova S.Sh.	
State of play of green finance in Uzbekistan: Opportunities for and barriers to green bond issuance	205
Voribaeva Z.P.	
Moliya va soliq sohasidagi muammolar yechim va xorijiy tajribalar	210
Toxirjonova Z.J.	
Тижорат банклари фойдасига солиқ солиш масалалари.....	212
Абдуллаев З.А.	
Банк хизматларига ҚҚС солиниш масалалари.....	214
Бисенбаев Ш.К.	
Европа тикланиш ва тараққиёт банкининг Ўзбекистондаги лойиҳаларни молиялаштиришдаги ўрни	217
Джумаев С.М.	
Қишлоқ хўжалигида суғурталаш масалалари	221
Иномжонов Ф.А.	
Islom moliyasi orqali loyihalarni moliyalashtirish tahlili.....	223
Komilov M.M.	
Компаниянинг қimmatли қоғозларга молиявий инвестицияларини баҳолаш механизмлари	226
Караев М.Ю.	

Исломиё молия тизимининг хусусиятлари	229
Маматов А.А.	
Эффект дохода и замещения в Европе.....	234
Сулаймонов А.	
Анализ изменений, влияющих на корпоративное управление коммерческих банков Узбекистана.....	237
Темиров А.А.	
Ўзбекистон республикасида пул муомаласини бошқаришнинг таҳлили.....	241
Астанов Ҳ.З.	
Improving the company's financial methods.....	243
Masharipova Sh.A., Bekbayeva F.B.	
Sug'urta faoliyati davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning zaruriyati va uning xorij tajribasi.....	247
O'razaliyev J.O'.	
Mikromoliyaviy xizmatlarning nazariy, normativ-huquqiy asoslari.....	250
Axmadaliyeva N.F., Egamberganov M.O.	
Банк хизматларига ққс солиниш масалалари	254
Бисенбаев Ш.К.	

4-SHO'BA. BIZNESNI BOSHQARISH VA IQTISODIYOT SOHASIDA RAQOBATBARDOSH KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI

Номарказлаштириш шароитида ҳудудий бошқарув тизимини такомиллаштириш.....	258
Қодиров А.М., Ахмедиева А.Т.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda elektron pullarning rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	262
Axmadaliyeva N.F., Abdujabborov Sh.A.	
O'zbekistonda faktoring xizmatlari bozorini rivojlantirish orqali iqtisodiyotda to'lov uzliksizligini ta'minlash yo'llari	265
Omonturdiyev O.E.	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish jarayonini iqtisodiy-statistik tahlil qilishning zamonaviy usullari (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida)	269
Nurxonov N.Q., Xalxadjayev B.B.	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida 2020 - 2030 yillarga mo'ljallangan qishloq ho'jaligini rivojlantirishda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash masallari	273
Djumanov T.A.	
The essence of the black economy	276
Rakhimova M., Abdusalamova U.	
Аудиторлик текширивунинг норматив-ҳуқуқий асослари	278
Абдуваитов Б.Б.	
Ҳудудларда тадбиркорлик субъектларини давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш.....	282
Бозоров И.И.	
Инвестицион лойиҳа рисклари моҳияти ва турлари.....	289
Душабоев Ж.Ж.	
Қишлоқ хўжалигида ер муносабатларини тартибга солишнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизми.....	294
Иноятова М.	
Деҳқон хўжаликлари ерларидан самарали фойдаланишини давлат томонидан рағбатлантириш йўллари	297
Садуллаев С.	
Олий таълим муассасаларида таълим лойиҳалари самарадорлигини ошириш.....	301
Рустамова Л. Р.	
Тикув-трикотаж маҳсулотларига маҳаллий истеъмолчилар талабини сегментлаш асосида маркетинг стратегияларини такомиллаштириш	305
Топилдиев С.Р.	

Озиқ-овқат маҳсулотлари бозорини давлат томонидан тартибга солиш воситалари.....	313
Даминова У.М.	
Анализ состояния и тенденций развития свободных экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	316
Кадинова И.Б.	
Moliyaviy va iqtisodiy muhitda qat'iy talablar bilan raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash	319
Qodirov F., Mavlonova M.N.	
Pedagogik amaliyot: muammo va yechimlar	321
Azim Davron	
Biznes sohasida raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash masalalari.....	323
Israilov P.I.	
Statistical analysis of the number of personnel working in agriculture.	325
Rustamova M.	
Biznesni boshqarish va iqtisodiyot sohasida raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlashning dolzarb masalalari va uning yechimlari.....	330
Xusenov Sh.Sh, Qurbonov B., Toshpo'latov B., Anarbayev S., Ro'ziboyev D., Boltayev A., Muxtorov M., Yondoshaliyev A., Abdumalikov N., Tursunaliyev U.	
Kichik va o'rta biznes rivojlanishini rag'batlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	333
Mamarayimova P.P.	
Kichik va o'rta biznesni qo'llab quvvatlashning xorij tajribasi uni Uzbekistonda qo'llash istiqbollari.	335
Toshboyev M.M.	
Преимущества внедрения технологии искусственного интеллекта предприятиями малого бизнеса.	337
Kalanova A.B.	
O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini shakllantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish.....	340
Yaxshiyeva M.T.	
Спорт менежменти тамойилларининг аҳамияти.....	343
Маматов М.	
Mahallalarda oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	348
Xodjamuratova G.Y., Yuldasheva D.K.	
Худудларнинг инвестицион имкониятларини оширишда кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорликни кредитлашни такомиллаштириш муаммолари.....	351
Бозоров И.И.	
Кичик ва ўрта бизнес учун яратилган МХХСларини амалга киритиш бўйича кўрсатмалар ва уларни республикада қўллашнинг аҳамияти	354
Муйдинов Э.Д.	
Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаси корхоналарини инновацион ривожлантририш механизмининг воситалари ва усуллари	357
Шарипова Б.Б.	
Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантририш моделлари.....	366
Шарипова Б.Б.	
O'zbekistonda uy-joy kommunal xizmatlarida audit tizimini takomillashtirish va raqamlashtirish.....	369
Primova Sh.K.	
Transport tashkilotlari moliyaviy holati auditining axborot bazasini tarkibi va mazmuni.....	372
Xudayberdiyev B.M.	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida inventarizatsiya natijalari tahlilining nazariy asoslari.....	375
Ruziyeva D.F.	
Ички аудитда далиллар тўплаш, муҳимликни аниқлаш ва рискларни баҳолаш усулларининг аҳамияти	377
Марданов М.Х.	

Темир йўл транспорти корхоналари фаолиятида ҳисоб сиёсатини қўллашнинг зарурати.....	379
Хужаев С.С.	
Таълим муассасаларида молиявий ҳисоботнинг ташкилий-услубий асослари ва аҳамияти	381
Исоқулов Ф.Ш.	
Inson resurslarini boshqarish. Karyerani rejalashtirish va rivojlantirish.....	383
Karimov V.A., Toshtemirov S.G., Ibodullayev N.I.	

5-SHO'BA. BIZNES VA BOSHQARUVDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT HAMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI

Влияние искусственного интеллекта на развитие экономики страны	387
Кузнецов В.П., Назарова Е.Н.	
Hududlarda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	390
Ma'murov B.X.	
The Impact of Digitalization on Sustainable World economy: Uzbekistan Case	394
Bakhtiyorov A.	
The importance of the digital platforms in the systematic development of the digital economy.....	397
Tal'atova D.B.	
Digitization of business.....	401
Rakhimova M.D., Allanazarov A.	
Transport-logistika tizimlari samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni.....	403
Matkarimov K.J.	
O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlanishini asosiy yo'nalishi	406
Karimjanova P., Abduraxmonov J.P.	
Biznes va boshqaruvda raqamli iqtisodiyot hamda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari	409
Qodirov F.E., Mavlonova M.N.	
Ways of future development of investment project risk insurance	411
Khakimzoda M.Y.	
Sintetik tola ishlab chiqarishni klaster usulida tashkil etishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi (Buxoro viloyati misolida)	413
Rahmonov Xurshid Xayriddinovich	
Biznesni boshqarishda sun'iy intellekt orqali qaror qabul qilish bosqichlari.....	416
Ro'ziboyev D.N., Tursunaliyev U., Abdumalikov N., Boltayev A., Yondoshaliyev A., Muxtorov M., Toshpo'latov B., Anarbayerov S., Qurbonov B., Xusenov Sh.	
Biznesda raqamli texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish	418
Israilov R.I.	
To'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi.....	420
Raxmatullaeva N.N., Abduqaxxorova A.B.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlanishida zamonaviy axborotlarni o'rni.....	424
Samatov Azizjon Abdulaxatovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati	426
Yelchibekov A.P., Asamxodjayeva Sh.Sh.	
Eksportda "Yagona oyna" tizimini qo'llash istiqbollari	428
Jo'rabayeva Sh.K.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot va suniy intellektning o'zaro integratsiyalashuvi.....	432
Toshpo'latov B., Xusenov Sh., Qurbonov B., Boltayev A., Muxtorov M., Yondoshaliyev A., Abdumalikov N., Tursunaliyev U., Anarbayerov S., Ro'ziboyev D.	
Tijorat banklari faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish yo'llari	435
Mirpulatova L.M.	

O'zbekistonda raqamli oziq-ovqat hamda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini rivojlantiruvchi indikatorlar.....	438
Abduraxmanova Z.T.	
Рақамли иқтисодиёт платформаларининг тузилиши ва ривожланиши.....	442
Имомова С.Ш.	
Динамика развития искусственного интеллекта.....	446
Абдураимова Н.Р.	
Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини тармоқлар ва уларнинг таркиби бўйича тақсимлаш модели.....	454
Шарипова Б.Б.	
Ўзбекистон Республикаси акциядорлик жамиятларида рақамли бошқарувни жорий этиш имкониятлари.....	457
Закирова Н.А.	
Sanoat sohasini jadal rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	461
Ismatulloeva M.F.	
Regulatory sandboxes and financial market education: empowering smes and retail investors for IPO participation.....	467
Saydullaev Sh.	
Способы, критерия и методы определение надежных поставщиков для государственных нужд.....	470
Карриев К.С.	
Chakana savdo korxonalarida reklama faoliyatini tashkil etish.....	478
Samadov A.N.	
Совершенствование системы управления инновационными проектами.....	485
Носиров Ж.Ж.	
Emotion detection in customer service: a cnn-based approach to employee engagement.....	491
Tangirov A.	
O'zbekiston taraqqiyotining yangi bosqichida iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlantirishning strategik jihatlari.....	494
Luqmanov B.M.	
Ўзбекистонни яшил иқтисодиётга ўтиш йўллари ва истиқболлари.....	500
Луқманов Б.М.	
A creative idea - the key to developing an innovative ecosystem.....	504
Alieva Elnara Ametovna	
Sun'iy intellektning hunarmandchilik mahsulotlari bozoridagi o'zni.....	507
Ergasheva Aziza Farmonovna	
O'zbekistonda oilaviy korxonalar faoliyatini boshqarishning hozirgi holati.....	510
Jurayev Navruz Jurayevich	
What drives financial development in Central Asian Countries.....	514
Bobojanov Shaxrux Qadamboyevich	
Online Advertising and its impact on consumer behavior.....	518
Ismailova Khanifajon	
O'zbekistonda yaylov yerlaridan samarali foydalanish va ekologik xavfsizligini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	520
Axmadaliev Voxob Abduraxmonovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	523
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'liqin qizi	
Искусственный интеллект: путь в будущее.....	528
Мурадов Фарход Джоракулович	
History of development and current state of artificial intelligence.....	531
Davronova Dilora Komiljonovna	

3-SHO'BA. **MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR,** **YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR**

METHODS

1. Budget Optimization:

Budgeting serves as the foundation of financial planning and control within organizations. However, traditional budgeting approaches often fall short in addressing the complexities of modern business environments. To optimize budgets effectively, companies are increasingly adopting flexible budgeting techniques, such as zero-based budgeting (ZBB) and activity-based budgeting (ABB). ZBB, championed by firms like Kraft Heinz and Unilever, involves scrutinizing expenses from scratch, thus eliminating inefficiencies and fostering a culture of cost-consciousness [3]. ABB, on the other hand, allocates resources based on the activities that drive costs, providing a more granular understanding of expenditure and enabling targeted cost reductions [4].

2. Forecasting Techniques:

Accurate forecasting is paramount for informed decision-making and proactive risk management. Traditional forecasting methods often rely on historical data and linear extrapolation, which may fail to capture nonlinear trends and external shocks. To enhance forecasting accuracy, companies are turning to advanced techniques such as predictive analytics and scenario modeling. Predictive analytics leverages machine learning algorithms to analyze large datasets and identify patterns, enabling organizations to anticipate future trends and make data-driven predictions [5]. Scenario modeling, meanwhile, allows businesses to simulate various scenarios and assess their financial implications under different market conditions, thereby enhancing strategic agility and resilience [6].

3. Cost Containment Measures:

Effective cost management is essential for optimizing profitability and preserving financial health. In addition to leveraging economies of scale and negotiating favorable supplier contracts, companies are exploring innovative cost containment measures such as lean management and process optimization. Lean management, pioneered by companies like Toyota, focuses on minimizing waste and maximizing value across the entire value chain, leading to significant cost savings and operational efficiencies [7]. Process optimization, facilitated by technologies like robotic process automation (RPA) and business process management (BPM) software, streamlines workflows and eliminates redundant tasks, driving down costs while enhancing productivity [8].

4. Capital Allocation Strategies:

Prudent capital allocation is crucial for maximizing shareholder value and supporting long-term growth initiatives. Traditional approaches to capital allocation often prioritize short-term returns over strategic objectives, leading to suboptimal investment decisions. To address this challenge, companies are adopting a more disciplined and strategic approach to capital allocation, guided by frameworks such as value-based management (VBM) and capital asset pricing model (CAPM). VBM emphasizes the creation of shareholder value through optimal resource allocation, aligning investment decisions with long-term value creation objectives [9]. CAPM, meanwhile, helps companies assess the risk-adjusted return of potential investments, enabling informed capital allocation decisions that balance risk and reward [10].

In conclusion, improving a company's financial methods is essential for driving sustainable growth, enhancing competitiveness, and maximizing shareholder value. By adopting innovative approaches to budget optimization, forecasting, cost containment, and capital allocation, organizations can strengthen their financial foundations and adapt proactively to evolving market dynamics. Through continuous innovation and strategic decision-making, businesses can position themselves for long-term success in an increasingly uncertain and complex business environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of Improved Financial Methods on Organizational Performance:

Enhancing a company's financial methods yields tangible benefits across various dimensions of organizational performance. Research indicates that firms adopting advanced financial methodologies experience improved financial performance metrics, including increased profitability, revenue growth, and shareholder value creation [11]. By optimizing budgeting processes, forecasting accuracy, cost containment measures, and capital allocation strategies, companies can bolster their financial resilience and competitiveness in today's dynamic business environment.

Budget Optimization:

The adoption of innovative budget optimization techniques such as zero-based budgeting (ZBB) and activity-based budgeting (ABB) enables organizations to reallocate resources more effectively, driving cost efficiencies and enhancing profitability. Companies that implement ZBB witness significant cost savings by scrutinizing expenses from the ground up, leading to a more efficient allocation of resources. Similarly, ABB provides a granular understanding of cost drivers, enabling targeted investments in value-creating activities

while minimizing wasteful expenditure [12]. Through these approaches, businesses can achieve greater budget discipline and strategic alignment, ultimately enhancing their financial performance.

Forecasting Accuracy:

Accurate forecasting is paramount for informed decision-making and risk management. By leveraging advanced predictive analytics and scenario modeling techniques, companies can anticipate future trends and assess potential outcomes under different scenarios. Predictive analytics empowers organizations to extract insights from vast amounts of data, enabling more accurate predictions of future performance and market dynamics [13]. Meanwhile, scenario modeling helps businesses evaluate the impact of various external factors on financial outcomes, enabling proactive risk mitigation and strategic planning. By improving forecasting accuracy, companies can make more informed investment decisions and adapt swiftly to changing market conditions, enhancing their competitiveness and resilience.

Cost Containment Measures:

Effective cost management is essential for maximizing profitability and preserving financial health. Lean management principles, combined with process optimization technologies such as robotic process automation (RPA) and business process management (BPM) software, enable organizations to streamline workflows and eliminate inefficiencies [14]. By minimizing waste and maximizing value across the value chain, companies can achieve significant cost savings while enhancing operational efficiency. Furthermore, strategic supplier partnerships and procurement initiatives contribute to cost reduction efforts, enabling businesses to negotiate favorable terms and achieve economies of scale. Through these cost containment measures, organizations can strengthen their financial position and improve overall profitability.

Capital Allocation Strategies:

Prudent capital allocation is critical for maximizing shareholder value and supporting long-term growth initiatives. By adopting value-based management (VBM) principles and leveraging frameworks such as the capital asset pricing model (CAPM), companies can prioritize investments that generate the highest risk-adjusted returns. VBM emphasizes the creation of shareholder value through optimal resource allocation, aligning investment decisions with long-term strategic objectives. Meanwhile, CAPM provides a systematic approach to assessing the risk-return profile of potential investments, enabling informed decision-making and portfolio optimization [15]. By employing disciplined capital allocation strategies, organizations can enhance their competitiveness and drive sustainable growth over the long term. Improving a company's financial methods has a profound impact on organizational performance, driving enhanced profitability, competitiveness, and shareholder value creation. By optimizing budgeting processes, enhancing forecasting accuracy, implementing cost containment measures, and adopting disciplined capital allocation strategies, businesses can strengthen their financial foundations and adapt proactively to changing market dynamics. Through continuous innovation and strategic decision-making, organizations can position themselves for sustained success in today's complex business environment.

CONCLUSION

In today's rapidly changing business landscape, the significance of robust financial methodologies cannot be overstated. The preceding discussion underscores the pivotal role of enhancing a company's financial methods in driving sustainable growth, bolstering competitiveness, and maximizing shareholder value creation. By optimizing budgeting processes, organizations can achieve greater transparency, discipline, and strategic alignment in resource allocation. Techniques such as zero-based budgeting and activity-based budgeting enable companies to eliminate inefficiencies, reallocate resources judiciously, and foster a culture of cost-consciousness.

Moreover, accurate forecasting serves as a cornerstone for informed decision-making and risk management. Leveraging advanced predictive analytics and scenario modeling techniques empowers businesses to anticipate market trends, assess potential outcomes, and adapt swiftly to changing circumstances.

Effective cost containment measures, including lean management principles and process optimization technologies, enable organizations to streamline workflows, minimize waste, and enhance operational efficiency. Strategic supplier partnerships and procurement initiatives further contribute to cost reduction efforts, enabling businesses to achieve economies of scale and improve profitability. Prudent capital allocation strategies, guided by frameworks such as value-based management and the capital asset pricing model, enable companies to prioritize investments that generate the highest risk-adjusted returns. By aligning investment decisions with long-term strategic objectives, organizations can enhance their competitiveness and drive sustained growth over time. In conclusion, improving a company's financial methods is imperative for navigating today's complex business environment successfully. Through continuous innovation, strategic decision-making, and

a commitment to excellence in financial management, organizations can position themselves for long-term success and resilience in the face of evolving market dynamics.

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

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Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.